

On the relation between the non-vacuous vacuum and quantum mechanics

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Whilst quantum mechanics is extremely successful in predicting and explaining the results of experiments in the microscopic domain, what physical quantity the wave function actually represents is still unknown and the paradoxes arising from it seem to have swapped one theoretical conundrum for bigger ones. In this paper, I intend to propose a conceptually different scheme to describe the motion of individual particle and meanwhile to obtain a statistical ensemble of particles position, resonating with the Copenhagen interpretation of the wave function, based on the observed fact that the vacuum is non-vacuous. By determining the physical meaning of de Broglie wavelength both on single and ensemble-event level, this theory is compatible with traditional quantum mechanics without violating the established principles and laws of it. More importantly, this scheme also intuitively explains the mysterious interference effect of particles without the necessity of introducing any counter-intuitive concept at all, which is fundamentally different from all existing versions but in excellent agreement with our common sense and hence naturally evading difficulties and paradoxes present in standard quantum mechanics.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is commonly believed that the vacuum is not vacuous but dominated by invisible components which will impose non-zero impacts on ordinary matter in an unusual way, based on the observations range from table-top experimental¹⁻⁵ to cosmological scales⁶⁻⁸. In this sense, on the basis of recent study on dark matter⁹⁻¹², we may reasonably conceive of a non-luminous granular substructure of matter underlying the vacuum space, analogous to (but not necessarily of exactly the same kind as) the air molecular structure underlying atmosphere, with weak interactions with ordinary matter and thus yielding momentum transfer to it (electron for example). In order to provide an accessible illustration, we can call this kind of granular component Particle X as we know little about it and regard this peculiar interaction as intuitive collision process.

By jointly taking into account the spatial symmetry and entropy principle, Particle X is inclined to be equally spaced in vacuum in staggered order, if we ignore their motion state in practice, exhibiting in a quincunx fashion, which is so much like a three-dimensional Galton board system¹³ with non-fixed pins. Therefore, the electron motion in vacuum without classical fields can be understood in terms of diffusion process due to random collisions with Particle X, which apparently follows Gaussian distribution obeying central limit theorem according to Galton board picture^{13,14} (as shown in FIG. 1a). Such that in effect we can obtain an exact description of free electron motion via a combination of the all possible steps, like leap-frog method. Incidentally, in a deeper dynamical sense, this behavior is somewhat analogous to Brownian-type motions under the influence of stochastic forces arising from interaction with a subquantum medium, which was favored by Bohm¹⁵ and other physicists¹⁶⁻¹⁹. For sake of simplicity, our discussion in this paper is restricted to the non-relativistic mechanics of particles without spin in the absence of classical fields, within two-dimensional framework and the extension to higher dimension is straightforward.

II. DETERMINISTIC TRAJECTORIES AND THE ROOT OF THE PROBABILITIES

In order to get a detailed description of the particles moving in vacuum, let us introduce an orthogonal coordinate system Oxy in the following way: an electron emitter is located y -axis at $y = L$ shooting electrons toward the origin with initial velocity v_0 , corresponding to initial momentum P_0 . A screen is placed at x -axis to register the electron's position information, as in FIG. 1a.

When flying in vacuum, the collision with Particle X will inevitably give rise to non-zero momentum transfer to electron. In this scheme, we do not fix our attention on the details of the inherently unanalyzable interaction process as other physicists did^{15,17,19,20}, but on the momentum transfer resulting from it. So let us invoke a parameter Δp_i to denote the momentum transfer due to i th kick, which can be orthogonally divided into $\Delta p_{x,i}$ and $\Delta p_{y,i}$ along the x -axis and y -axis respectively, for ease of calculation. As a vector, the change of momentum component can be positive or negative indicating their directions (all the vector parameters in this article are in **boldface** expression). Accordingly, the recipe for calculating the cumulative information of momentum evolving after suffering j collisions is quite straightforward, which can be given by:

$$P_{x,j} = \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta p_{x,i} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{y,j} = P_0 + \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta p_{y,i} \quad (2)$$

where $P_{x,j}$ and $P_{y,j}$ indicates the momentum corresponding to x -axis and y -axis respectively after j kicks, as in Fig 1b. Considering quantum effect is just important at the atomic level but negligible at the macroscopic level, the momentum perturbation should be extremely weak in reality, namely

FIG. 1. The illustration of electron motion in vacuum space. Combination of blue solid arrows constitutes the electron trajectory. (a) Schematic view of the coordinate system. An electron emitter (blue spotted cylinder) is placed at $(0, L)$ shooting electrons (blue spots) toward the origin with initial momentum \mathbf{P}_0 . The black dots, uniformly distributed in a staggered order, represent the non-luminous Particle X, forming a two-dimensional Galton board. Accordingly, electrons' location in x -axis direction should follow Gaussian distribution as the black dashed curve shows. (b) Magnified view of the momentum transfer regime. The solid green and magenta arrow represent the momentum transfer $\Delta \mathbf{p}_i$ due to i th kick and the momentum evolution \mathbf{P}_j after j kicks respectively (in this illustration, $j = i - 1$). To facilitate calculation, each of them can be decomposed into orthogonal vectors along x -axis and y -axis as the dashed arrows indicate.

$\Delta p_{y,i} \ll P_0$, so it is reasonable for us to make an approximation in which the last term in Eq. (2) can be neglected and this equation reduces to $\mathbf{P}_{y,j} \approx \mathbf{P}_0$. Thus, it is permissible to consider the velocity in y -axis direction as constant with initial value v_0 in this approximation.

To proceed further, let us refer Δt_j to the time interval between j th and $(j+1)$ st collision, while δt_0 and δt_n denotes the time interval before the first and after the last, namely the n th collision respectively, with n denoting the total number (typically very large but not infinite) of random collisions during the given time t . In this scheme, collisions are considered to be instantaneous, so any given time t can be rigorously presented as:

$$t = \delta t_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \Delta t_j + \delta t_n \quad (3)$$

Opposite to differentiating this motion process, which yields the Hamilton–Jacobi equation from the classical variational problem minimizing the action integral in usual ways^{17,19}, within this framework, we can straightforwardly reconstruct the electron's trajectory by summing over all possible jumps according to the classical cognition that electron is flying in a uniform linear motion between collisions in the field-free space as following equations:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \frac{\mathbf{P}_{x,j}}{m_e} \cdot \Delta t_j + \frac{\mathbf{P}_{x,n}}{m_e} \cdot \delta t_n \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_t = L - l \approx L - v_0 t \quad (5)$$

Here, \mathbf{x}_t and \mathbf{y}_t are the coordinates of the electron's actual position at a given moment of time t , and m_e is the mass of electron, with l being the distance the electron travels along the y -axis during this period.

Next, considering the Particle X distributes uniformly within this framework, if the number of collisions n is large enough, the discrepancy between time intervals should be practically indistinguishable. Thus, both Δt_i and δt_n are roughly equal to $\bar{\Delta t}$ which represents the mean time interval between two consecutive collisions, that is $\bar{\Delta t} = \frac{t}{n}$. Then, substituting equation (1) into (4), we can get:

$$\mathbf{x}_t \approx \frac{t}{nm_e} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta \mathbf{p}_{x,i} \quad (6)$$

If we substitute the equation, $t = \frac{l}{v_0}$, into equation (6), thus it can be rephrased in the absence of time t as following equation:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \frac{l}{nP_0} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta \mathbf{p}_{x,i} \quad (7)$$

To study this scheme in more depth, let us introduce another crucial parameter ρ_r defined as linear density of Particle X in vacuum, which indicates the number of collisions an electron may undergo when flying per unit length, in writing equation $\rho_r = \frac{n}{s}$ with s being the distance an electron flying through. Obviously, ρ_r is closely relate to the volume distribution density of Particle X in vacuum which can be regarded as constant in a given space. If $l \gg |\mathbf{x}_t|$, l can reasonably approximate to s , so Eq. (7) can be recast as following:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \frac{1}{\rho_r P_0} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{\rho_r \cdot l} \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta \mathbf{p}_{x,i} \quad (8)$$

As discussed above, it is pretty clear that the electron has a definite momentum and position at all time and follows a deterministic trajectory, however predicting the path information is still not permitted even with these approximations we have made, in that the last term in Eq. (6) is a stochastic variable

which is highly sensitive to the random characters of collision process, more specifically, the collision angle and velocity of the flying electron relative to the Particle X, which should be inherently uncontrollable and unpredictable. In other words, one cannot know the positions of the electron any more accurately than standard quantum mechanics allows.

Then probability decisively enters into this presenting theory from the recognition that a statistical ensemble of collisions will lead to a corresponding statistical ensemble of changes in particle positions. According to Galton board model, electrons' location in transverse direction will follow Gaussian distribution due to central limit theorem^{13,14}. Therefore, we can get the exact probability distributions for the position of the electrons located at x-axis by using Gauss formula $f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-(x-\bar{x})^2/(2\sigma^2)}$, where \bar{x} denotes the mathematical expectation which is zero in this regime with a spatial-symmetric view, with σ being the variance of distribution. Thus the probability density of the electron presence at the position $x \sim x+r$ on screen (denoted by P_r) can be obtained by $P_r = \int_x^{x+r} \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-x^2/(2\sigma^2)}dx$, which is mathematically equivalent to the modulus squared of the Schrödinger function with respect to Gaussian wave packet and at the same time obviously satisfies the normalization condition, conforming to the Born rule of standard quantum mechanics.

To investigate the statistical ensemble property of all possible events, we should turn the spotlight to the variance of distribution σ which can be calculated using the following well-known formula:

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{(x_k - \bar{x})^2}{N} = \sum_{k=1}^N x_k^2 \frac{1}{N} \quad (9)$$

where N denotes the total number of all possible trajectories, each one for an emitting electron, theoretically infinite but as a practical matter we can truncate the series at a desired level of accuracy, with x_k being the electron's coordinate position located in screen corresponding to the k th path, or saying the k th electron.

Therefore, it can be seen that, in this scheme, what is really meaningful with actual physical significance is not the spatial information of the electron, but rather the sum of square modulus of the position information corresponding to each path, which, in practical, has some in common with Feynman's diagram for path integrals²¹. In this setup, l equals to L , and we substitute Eq. (8) into Eq. (9), thus it can be straightforwardly recast as:

$$\sigma^2 = \left(\frac{1}{\rho_r P_0} \right)^2 \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\rho_r L} \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta^k p_{x,i} \right)^2 \frac{1}{N} \quad (10)$$

Here, vector $\Delta^k p_{x,i}$ represents the momentum transfer in x-axis direction due to i th kick in the k th trajectory. For sake of brevity, we now define an equation:

$$\sigma'^2 = \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\sum_{j=1}^{\rho_r L} \sum_{i=1}^j \Delta^k p_{x,i} \right)^2 \frac{1}{N} \quad (11)$$

which apparently is a function of the distance of the electron flying, the magnitude of momentum disturbance by surrounding vacuum and the linear distribution density of Particle X, respectively analogous to the ball release height, restitution coefficient and the distribution density of nails in Galton-board system^{14,22}, in some sense. Then, the distribution variance can be simplified as:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho_r P_0} \sigma' \quad (12)$$

where σ' implicitly indicates the property of the vacuum space the electron moving through.

To complete the connection with quantum mechanics, let us substitute the famous de Broglie wavelength equation, $\lambda = \frac{h}{p}$, into Eq. (12), and we can get:

$$\sigma = \lambda \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma'}{\rho_r h} \right) \quad (13)$$

where λ denotes the de Broglie wavelength and h is the Planck constant. Then it is clear that de Broglie wavelength is physically proportional to the distribution variance, on the ensemble-event level. In other words, a particle with longer matter wavelength indicates that it probably move in the trajectory with more deviation from classical expectation, namely being more unpredictable for the path information, like a leaf floating down if we regard the Particle X as air molecules, evolving according to the mechanics presented in this article which is mathematically and physically equivalent to the standard quantum mechanics (not necessarily identical with same parameter). Conversely, an object with shorter wavelength means that it will pursue a more definite course in line with the classical physical, like an apple falling down, evolving according to the Newtonian mechanics.

III. DOUBLE-SLIT EXPERIMENT AND PARADOXES

When discussing the particle analog of Thomas Young's double-slit experiment with electrons, Richard Feynman stated that "a phenomenon which is impossible, absolutely impossible to explain in any classical way, and which has in it the heart of quantum mechanics. In reality, it contains the only mystery."²³ In what follows, I intend to rise the challenge within this proposing framework without having to say that each electron passes through both slits simultaneously as if it were a wave^{21,23}, either having to say that there is "pilot wave"^{24,25} or "supersense"²⁶ in surrounding physical space.

To begin with, let us zoom in on such a system and observe the electron's trajectory more closely. Then it is vital to put away the conventional prejudice that an electron moves on a straight path in vacuum space without classical field, but accept the fact that it follows an irregularly zigzag trajectory from the description in the preceding section. For subsequent discussion, it is necessary here to invoke a new scalar variable " Λ " to quantify the extent of path tortuosity, which can be done with the transverse deviation distance from the expected

FIG. 2. Diagram of the characteristic of electron trajectory. Blue dashed arrows indicate the expected path without collisions. The magenta dotted lines represent the transverse displacement from the position it would have had in the absence of the collision, which directly indicates the extent of the tortuosity of electron trajectory (denoted by Λ). Self-consistently, within this framework, Λ is physically equivalent to the de Broglie wavelength (λ), on the average.

position due to per collision (as shown in FIG. 2), in writing equation:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\Delta p_{x,i}}{m_e} \cdot \Delta t_i = \frac{\Delta p_{x,i}}{m_e} \cdot \frac{l}{nv_o} = \frac{1}{P_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta p_{x,i}}{\rho_r} \quad (14)$$

where Δt_i denotes the time interval between the i th and $(i + 1)$ st collision, which equals to the mean time interval between two consecutive collisions within this framework. Substituting de Broglie wavelength equation into Eq. (14), we get:

$$\Lambda = \lambda \cdot \frac{\Delta p_{x,i}}{h\rho_r} \quad (15)$$

Then, the last term in Eq.(15) can be defined as vacuum coefficient c_v , that is $c_v = \frac{\Delta p_{x,i}}{h\rho_r}$ which illustrates the correlation between the strength of electron-Particle X interplay and the linear distribution density of Particle X in vacuum space. If it takes value around one, it is intriguing to note that the variable Λ is physically equivalent to λ on the average. This means that the de Broglie wavelength can generally manifest itself as zigzag extent of trajectory, on the single-event level. Obviously, in this case the relationship between the mean strength of momentum perturbation by per collision (denoted by $\overline{\Delta p_{x,i}}$), and the linear distribution density of Particle X satisfies the following equation:

$$\frac{\overline{\Delta p_{x,i}}}{\rho_r} = h \quad (16)$$

which supports the desired features of vacuum space owing to the smallness of Planck's constant, specifically referring to the large enough collision number during electron's flight and extremely feeble momentum disturbance by kicks with Particle X, and thereby in turn guarantees the self-consistency of this proposing theory.

Now consider a double-slit experiment apparatus. If the slit width a is much larger than the tortuous extent of electron's

trajectories, which can be equivalently represented by $a \gg \lambda$, then it is admissible to ignore their tortuous feature, and regard those trajectories as straight lines. Hence, the discrepancy between the angles of emanating electrons when passing through the slits is negligible. Such that there will be only two illuminations about the position which is located on a straight line with the electron emitter and corresponding slit (as in FIG. 3a), behaving as a classical particle-like regime.

Following the line of this thought, however, if these trajectories can apparently exhibit their zigzag property on the backdrop of the slit width, translated into wave language is that if the slit width a is comparable to the de Broglie wavelength which is the situation when interference effect appears, the discrepancy between the angles at which electrons zigzag from the slit will arise particularly significant (not just un-negligible) and consequently give rise to fundamentally different phenomena from above situation. Specifically, electrons in this experimental setup will be scattered out from slits in discretely different directions due to their tortuous motion characteristic, and each flight direction will produce a bright fringe fading bilaterally obeying central limit theorem as demonstrated in the previous section, thus yielding alternately bright and dark stripes after a large number of repetitive emissions. If there are several slits (most conveniently analyzed in a double-slit setup), in the overlapping region, the contributions from corresponding slits should add up in classical way, and then the so-called interference phenomenon appears (as shown diagrammatically in Fig. 3b).

That is, we now qualitatively show that, in our interpretation, these stripes are not caused by the electron counter-intuitively interfering itself, behaving as a wave-like regime as usual interpretations described^{21,23}, but originated from their saw-toothed trajectory due to its stochastic interaction with the surrounding sub-quantum medium. While as intuitive and aesthetically appealing as it is, this is not a rigorous mathematical argument. Consequently, firm conclusions may not be drawn at this stage, but it would seem that the assumption of particles with precisely defined positions in this unified scheme is likely to be on the right track, at least in its essential features. In order to verify this mechanism macroscopically, I used a self-made apparatus based on the present scheme to mimic the single electron double-slit experiment and corresponding stripes were successfully reproduced in Fig.3c and see more detailed description of the setup and movie from <https://zenodo.org/record/4139502#.X5gYUIgzZPY>.

Since, apparently, this proposing scheme does not set the limits²⁷ where the "quantum-to-classical transition" happens, it provides a more natural way to explain the "interference pattern" of macromolecules, especially those with much larger size than their own de Broglie wavelength^{28,29}. Besides, with the aid of the visualized interpretation (FIG. 3b), it is not difficult to see that the visibility of the fringes is proportional to the discrepancy of emitting angles from slits, as well as the vertical distance (d) between two-slit structure and screen. Considering the angular discrepancy is probably in proportion to the zigzag extent of trajectory, namely de Broglie wavelength, the relation can be given by:

$$V \propto (d\&\lambda) \quad (17)$$

FIG. 3. Simplified schematic of the double-slit experiment. Owing to central limit theorem, electrons from left and right slit will respectively distribute as magenta and green solid curves indicate, centering around the dashed lines with corresponding colors which represent the directions when electrons passing through the slits. Strictly speaking, these curves should be skewed distribution in that the flight direction is not perpendicular to the screen, but that doesn't affect the demonstration of the nature of this interpretation. (a) Diagram of classical particle-like regime. If the tortuous extent of electron trajectories is taken to be negligible compared to the slit width, it is admissible to regard them as straight lines and hence there will be only two illuminations located behind the two slits. (b) Diagram of wave-like regime. On the other hand, if the slit width is comparable to the tortuous extent, or saying the de Broglie wavelength, electrons will scatter out from slits in discretely different directions and each flight direction will produce a bright fringe fading bilaterally, then "interference phenomenon" appears. In the overlapping region, the two contributions from two slits should add up in classical way as represented by the black solid curve, instead of interference way. (c) The reproduction of the "interference pattern" by using a self-made double slits apparatus based on the present scheme (supplementary movie is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/4139502#.X5gYUIgzZPY>).

where V denotes the distance between two adjacent maxima distributions, representing the visibility of the fringes. Then it is clear that this relation agrees qualitatively with the theoretical calculation according to standard quantum mechanics³⁰.

Contrary to the orthodox quantum mechanics but consistent with our common sense, in this suggested physical picture, the electron obviously occupies only one definite position in space at any given moment, never being "here" and "there" simultaneously, a phenomenon defined as the principle of superposition state according to standard quantum theory. Likewise, consider again, the Schrödinger's cat²¹ was either dead or alive, never being in two superposing states. (Except that when it was in brain death due to inhaling a lethal dose of cyanide gas, then its state was indeed determined by the local law.)

Moreover, from the above analysis, we have seen that a particle's path information is fully deterministic whether we intend to watch it or not. However, any attempt of measurement to obtain the path information of the particle by shining light on it or emitting photons from it, or more generally speaking the unavoidable interaction between this particle and measurement apparatus, will physically lead to random momentum perturbation (rather than split our living universe into a multitude of mutually unobservable but equally real worlds³¹), which correspondingly yields stochastic displacement of transverse position according to Eq. (6) in line with the present framework, thus potentially washing out the interference effect. Evidently, the more which-way information one obtains, which in turn renders the more momentum disturbance, the more loss of interference phenomenon will take place. This, in essence, is similar to the Feynman's electron-light scattering scheme²³ and also shows excellent agreement

with Heisenberg's position-momentum uncertainty principle both theoretically³²⁻³⁴ and experimentally³⁵⁻³⁹.

In this interpretation, the necessity for this destruction is not inherent in the conceptual structure; and as we shall see, the destruction of the interference pattern could in principle be avoided by means of other ways of making measurements, ways which are weak enough to measure a quantum particle without appreciably disturbing it⁴⁰. Accordingly, by using weak-measurement scheme, Steinberg et al.⁴¹ and Kazufumi Sakai⁴² have succeed in obtaining both particle-like trajectories information and wavelike interference pattern simultaneously in their own double-slit interferometer, which is in radical violation of complementarity viewed as the fundamental principle of standard quantum mechanics, but fits comfortably within this proposing theory.

Given the information we have at present, we can speak out confidently that we live in an objective and unique world, in which we don't have to keep staring at the moon to keep it from disappearing or have to worry about the world splitting into different branches due to our measurement processes.

IV. A DISTINGUISHABLE EXPERIMENT

Based on the deduction from the above statements, electron always behaves as a particle and goes through only one slit in the double-slit apparatus in conformity with our human intuition, leaving no room for the weird wave-particle duality. Besides, there is also no pilot wave passing through both slits simultaneous or any other counterintuitive concepts which can "supersense" another slit is open or closed. Thus, we can conclude that the trajectories of electrons when both

slits are open should be no different from the trajectories when only one slit is open. That is to say, in this present scheme, the intensity when both slits are open is equal to the sum of the intensities corresponding to the situation when only one slit is open and the other is closed, which is in stark contradiction with the prediction of standard quantum mechanics. In this way, it opens the possibility to unambiguously distinguish this present scheme from orthodox quantum mechanics with the aid of the canonical modified double-slit experiment as described below, which was taken for so granted that physicists were always imagining the result by thought experiment, instead of validating it through rigid test.

Back to the double-slit experiment, working in such a way that when we keep one slit open and the other one closed, shoot a lot of electrons and switch the order and shoot electrons again similarly. In this case, if the bar-code-like pattern that is a hallmark of wavelike behavior doesn't show up, as imagined by adherents of orthodox quantum mechanics^{21,23}, the theory proposed in this paper will be undoubtedly falsified and discarded as an invalid theory, and the standard quantum mechanics in our belief will be reinforced again. On the contrary, if the alternately bright and dark stripes, namely interference pattern, still appears, which can only be explained within this current framework, then some rewritings will probably take place in the chapters of textbook with regard to the mysterious wave property of particles.

V. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVE

In this paper, we have showed that the scheme presented here, although not expressed in terms of a compact differential equation, has the advantage of being physically intuitive in the explanation of the nature of probabilities and provides the exact reproduction of the statistical results of quantum mechanics, along with determining the physical meaning of de Broglie wavelength, a concept arising from standard quantum mechanics. What's more important, the interpretation we adopt within this framework also perfectly applies to the famous double-slit experiment, as well as the infamous measurement problem, by means of classical physics, which allows a new reconciliation with our common sense, thereby being free of such difficulties and paradoxes posed by conventional quantum mechanics. So, I am encouraged to believe that this theory, although in preliminary stage of development, will provide a glimpse of the complex nature of some physical phenomena and potentially sheds light on the dark sides of the universe.

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¹Casimir HB. On the attraction between two perfectly conducting plates. *Front. Phys.* 1948; 100:61-63.

- ²Lamoreaux SK. Demonstration of the Casimir force in the 0.6 to 6 μm range. *Phys Rev Lett* 1997; 78:5.
- ³Wilson CM, Johansson G, Pourkabirian A, Simoen M, Johansson JR, Duty T, et al. Observation of the dynamical Casimir effect in a superconducting circuit. *Nature* 2011; 479:376-379.
- ⁴Lamb Jr WE, Retherford RC. Fine structure of the hydrogen atom by a microwave method. *Physical Review* 1947; 72:241.
- ⁵Fragner A, Göppl M, Fink JM, Baur M, Bianchetti R, Leek PJ, et al. Resolving vacuum fluctuations in an electrical circuit by measuring the Lamb shift. *Science* 2008; 322:1357-1360.
- ⁶Babcock HW. The rotation of the Andromeda Nebula. *Lick Observatory Bulletin* 1939; 19:41-51.
- ⁷Rubin VC, Ford Jr WK, Thonnard N. Rotational properties of 21 SC galaxies with a large range of luminosities and radii, from NGC 4605/R= 4kpc/ to UGC 2885/R= 122 kpc. *The Astrophysical Journal* 1980; 238:471-487.
- ⁸Clowe D, Bradač M, Gonzalez AH, Markevitch M, Randall SW, Jones C, et al. A direct empirical proof of the existence of dark matter. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 2006; 648:L109.
- ⁹Caldwell R, Kamionkowski M. Dark matter and dark energy. *Nature* 2009; 458:587-589.
- ¹⁰Bertone G. The moment of truth for WIMP dark matter. *Nature* 2010; 468:389-393.
- ¹¹Barkana R. Possible interaction between baryons and dark-matter particles revealed by the first stars. *Nature* 2018; 555:71-74.
- ¹²Chan MH. A universal constant for dark matter-baryon interplay. *Sci Rep-Uk* 2019; 9:1-8.
- ¹³Kunert J, Montag A, Pöhlmann S. The quincunx: history and mathematics. *Stat Pap* 2001; 42:143-169.
- ¹⁴Rosato AD, Blackmore D, Buckley L, Oshman C, Johnson M. Experimental, simulation and nonlinear dynamics of Galton's board. *Int J Nonlin Sci Num* 2004; 5:289-312.
- ¹⁵Bohm D. A suggested interpretation of the quantum theory in terms of "hidden" variables. I. *Physical review* 1952; 85:166.
- ¹⁶Bohm D, Vigier J. Model of the causal interpretation of quantum theory in terms of a fluid with irregular fluctuations. *Physical Review* 1954; 96:208.
- ¹⁷Nelson E. Derivation of the Schrödinger equation from Newtonian mechanics. *Physical review* 1966; 150:1079.
- ¹⁸Grössing G, Fussy S, Pascasio JM, Schwabl H. An explanation of interference effects in the double slit experiment: Classical trajectories plus ballistic diffusion caused by zero-point fluctuations. *Ann Phys-New York* 2012; 327:421-437.
- ¹⁹Ohsumi A. An interpretation of the Schrödinger equation in quantum mechanics from the control-theoretic point of view. *Automatica* 2019; 99:181-187.
- ²⁰Couder Y, Protiere S, Fort E, Boudaoud A. Walking and orbiting droplets. *Nature* 2005; 437:208.
- ²¹Greenberger D, Hentschel K, Weinert F. *Compendium of quantum physics: concepts, experiments, history and philosophy*. Springer Science & Business Media 2009.
- ²²Bruno L, Calvo A, Ippolito I. Dispersive flow of disks through a two-dimensional Galton board. *The European Physical Journal E* 2003; 11:131-140.
- ²³Feynman RP, Leighton RB, Sands M. *The Feynman lectures on physics, Vol. I: The new millennium edition: mainly mechanics, radiation, and heat*. Basic books 2011.
- ²⁴Bell JS. De Broglie-Bohm, delayed-choice, double-slit experiment, and density matrix. *Int J Quantum Chem* 1980; 18:155-159.
- ²⁵Božić M, Marić Z, Vigier JP. De Broglie probabilities in the double-slit experiment. *Found Phys* 1992; 22:1325-1344.
- ²⁶Aharonov Y, Cohen E, Colombo F, Landsberger T, Sabadini I, Struppa DC, et al. Finally making sense of the double-slit experiment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2017; 114:6480-6485.
- ²⁷Arndt M, Hornberger K. Testing the limits of quantum mechanical superpositions. *Nat Phys* 2014; 10:271-277.
- ²⁸Arndt M, Nairz O, Vos-Andreae J, Keller C, Van der Zouw G, Zeilinger A. Wave-particle duality of C₆₀ molecules. *Nature* 1999; 401:680-682.
- ²⁹Gerlich S, Eibenberger S, Tomandl M, Nimmrichter S, Hornberger K, Fagan PJ, et al. Quantum interference of large organic molecules. *Nat Commun* 2011; 2:1-5.

- ³⁰Carnal O, Mlynek J. Young's double-slit experiment with atoms: A simple atom interferometer. *Phys Rev Lett* 1991; 66:2689.
- ³¹DeWitt BS, Graham N. *The many worlds interpretation of quantum mechanics*. Princeton University Press 2015.
- ³²Bohm D. A Suggested Interpretation of the Quantum Theory in Terms of "Hidden" Variables. II. *Physical Review* 1952; 85:180.
- ³³Storey P, Tan S, Collett M, Walls D. Path detection and the uncertainty principle. *Nature* 1994; 367:626-628.
- ³⁴Wiseman HM. Bohmian analysis of momentum transfer in welcher Weg measurements. *Phys Rev a* 1998; 58:1740.
- ³⁵Scully MO, Englert B, Walther H. Quantum optical tests of complementarity. *Nature* 1991; 351:111-116.
- ³⁶Hornberger K, Uttenthaler S, Brezger B, Hackermüller L, Arndt M, Zeilinger A. Collisional decoherence observed in matter wave interferometry. *Phys Rev Lett* 2003; 90:160401.
- ³⁷Hackermüller L, Hornberger K, Brezger B, Zeilinger A, Arndt M. Decoherence of matter waves by thermal emission of radiation. *Nature* 2004; 427:711-714.
- ³⁸Mir R, Lundeen JS, Mitchell MW, Steinberg AM, Garretson JL, Wiseman HM. A double-slit 'which-way' experiment on the complementarity-uncertainty debate. *New J Phys* 2007; 9:287.
- ³⁹Xiao Y, Wiseman HM, Xu J, Kedem Y, Li C, Guo G. Observing momentum disturbance in double-slit "which-way" measurements. *Sci Adv* 2019; 5:v9547.
- ⁴⁰Cho A. Physics. Furtive approach rolls back the limits of quantum uncertainty. *Science (New York, NY)* 2011; 333:690.
- ⁴¹Kocsis S, Braverman B, Ravets S, Stevens MJ, Mirin RP, Shalm LK, et al. Observing the average trajectories of single photons in a two-slit interferometer. *Science* 2011; 332:1170-1173.
- ⁴²Sakai K. Simultaneous measurement of wave and particle properties using modified Young's double-slit experiment. *Journal for Foundations and Applications of Physics* 2018; 5:49-54.